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Morphological Characterization of Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) Accessions Collected in the Centre-west, South-west and West of Côte d'Ivoire

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ABSTRACT

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is an important food crop in Côte d'Ivoire. Nonetheless, its production is facing many constraints including the abandonment of landraces, fires, pests and diseases. Such a pressure can cause an erosion of the genetic diversity of cassava and wild relatives. In order to overcome those constraints, collections of traditional varieties were carried out in the Centre-west, South-west and West of Côte d'Ivoire. A total of 159 accessions were used. These accessions were observed using morphological parameter. Morphological characterization was done through multivariate analyses on these 159 accessions to better manage germplasm. Accessions were clustered into three classes with 143 morphotypes and 16 duplicates. Class 1 or Type Sié, composed of 45 accessions, included the majority of accessions that had the least common modalities of collection (yellow flesh, white skin, yellowish phelloderm and orange stem). Analysis of similarity / dissimilarity showed that clusters known as Sié, Bassié djélé4 and Djonan djonan of the current germplasm were close to different groups Cosca4, D14 and 256 of the existing collection.

Keywords:

Cassava, *Manihot esculenta*,
accession cluster, morphological
characterization

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is the fifth largest food crop after maize, rice, wheat and potato in the world (FAO, 2014). Its global production is estimated at 263.58 million tons in 2012 (FAO, 2014). Cassava contributes not only to the food and feed but it is also used in manufactures (textile, paper, etc.). According to Aka (2009), cassava is the most important food crop in Africa with more than 113 million tons of tuberous roots and their processing products are consumed.

In Côte d'Ivoire, cassava is the second largest food crop after yam, with a production of 2.41 million tons in 2012 (FAO, 2014). Production covers all the national territory with a higher area located in the South. Cassava is rustic and is both food and cash crops for producers. It provides multiple local products (cuscus-like attiéké, foutou, dough-like toh, flour, starch, gari, among others) which are intended for national and regional trade (N'Zué, 2007).

However, due to the actions of producers who often give up cultivars, and due to the pressure of biotic and abiotic stresses such as bush fires and pests and diseases, cassava and its related wild species are gradually subjected to the genetic drift (N'Zué, 2007). Therefore, it is necessary to limit the erosion by collection, conservation and sustainable management of local genetic resources. Regardless, the method used (mass selection, crossbreeding, genetic engineering among others) for the creation of new varieties, rural communities and research institutes need local genetic resources that have hard characters favorable to stable yields (Dantsey-Barry and Kpemoua, 2003). In addition, plant genetic resources are the key to food security and sustainable agricultural development (Diouf *et al.*, 2007).

Many studies of characterization have been carried out on the genetic resources of cassava. Thus, in Congo, Kombo *et al.* (2012) classified 86 cassava cultivars into 36 agrotypes, based on agronomic and culinary characters. In Benin, 19 traits related to agronomic and technological descriptions of varieties allowed to Odjo (2010) to classify 63 varieties into four main groups. In Côte d'Ivoire, the work achieved by Zoundjihékpon (1986) on the morphophysiological characterization showed that from qualitative or quantitative characteristics observed and measured, it is possible to cluster the genetic resources of cassava into more homogeneous classes. Morphological characterization performed by N'Zué (2007) allowed the clustering of 340 accessions from the collection of CNRA (Centre National de Recherche Agronomique) into eight (8) homogeneous classes. According to the author, the assessment and characterization could make efficient the management and use of several genebanks. However, cassava accessions newly collected in farmers' fields in the regions of Centre-west, South-west, and Western of Côte d'Ivoire had not yet been characterized in term of morphological, agronomic, enzymatic or molecular parameters. While it may be that a cultivar is present in the collected germplasm in multiple specimens.

The morphological characterization could reveal morphological variability and duplicates within current germplasm. It could also cluster accessions into eight classes and establish corresponding between current and existing germplasms.

The objective of this study was to evaluate and characterize the genetic resources of cassava collected in areas of Côte d'Ivoire for rational conservation and management purposes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection sites, trial localization and plant material

Cassava accessions were collected in the Centre-west, South-west and Western areas of Côte d'Ivoire. These areas are located at longitudes 6°41'-8°02' West and latitudes 4°30'-6°34' (Figure 1).

The collection of the Centre-west was made in the Gagnoa, Issia and Sinfra regions. Semi-deciduous dense forest characterizes vegetation. Annual rainfall varied between 1416 mm and 1603 mm from 2008 to 2010 (Kouadio, 2013).

For South-west region, the study was done at Grand-Bereby and Tabou. This region is dominated by evergreen rainforest. The annual rainfall ranged from 1514 mm to 2358 mm from 2008 to 2010 (Kouadio, 2013).

In the West one, the prospection was done at Guiglo, Taï, Grabo and Bloléquin. Its vegetation is evergreen rainforest. Annual rainfall varied between 1600 mm and 2000 mm (Sangare *et al.*, 2009). In all three regions, soils are moderately or strongly desaturated and ferrallitic (Perraud, 1967).

The trial was set up at the experimental site of the CNRA based on Adiopodoumé in South of Côte d'Ivoire (Figure 1). Dense evergreen forest dominates the vegetation with a bimodal rainfall regime. Annual rainfall varied between 1581 mm and 2267 mm from 2009 to 2010 (Kouamé *et al.*, 2010). Lateritic soils are highly desaturated (Perraud, 1967).

The plant material consisted of 159 accessions of cassava collected in 26 villages. All of them belonged to the species *M. esculenta* and were divided as follows: (i) 69 accessions collected in the Centre-west of Côte d'Ivoire, (ii) 46 accessions harvested in the South-west of the country and (iii) 44 accessions were harvested at West of country.

Experimental design

The trial was carried out in Fisher design with 2 replicates (or blocks). The land was manually cleared and plowed. Each block was divided, along its length, into two bands. Each band was subdivided, at its turn, into individual plot each receiving one accession. A number of 159 plots per block were used. The plot included 2 rows of 6 plants per row with spacings 0.8 m (rows) x 0.8 m (plants) and 1.5 m between plots. Bands and blocks were separate as 1.5 m between bands and 2 m between blocks. Cuttings (20-30 cm or

4-6 comprising nodes) were horizontally planted on ploughed soil at a depth of less than 10 cm. Weeding was done if necessary. Harvest was carried out 12 months after planting.

Observations

Observations were done using morphological descriptors which were considered qualitative or slightly variable in different environments for a given variety. They were identical to those used by N'Zué (2007) when he morphologically characterized the base cassava collection. N'Zué took into account his personal observations and descriptors used by Cours (1951) and Léfèvre (1988) in order to characterize the maximum accessions. Indeed, the variables used were also part of the list of morphological selected characters by IITA (Fukuda *et al.*, 2010) for the characterization of cassava. Each of the 159 collected accessions was characterized by 14 characters with modalities varying from 2 to 4 (Table 1). The observations were made in either block where the shapes of the accessions had few attacks or deformations caused by pests. They were as follows:

- a) for leaves and stem, the traits that observed 5 months after planting, were apical leaf colour, leaf vein colour, petiole colour, mature leaf colour, apical stem colour and mature leaf shape;
- b) for tuberous roots, observations were made at harvest and included peduncle, shape of tuberous roots, epidermis colour, phelloderm colour, and pulp colour;
- c) for other organs, three descriptors (flowering, branching habit, and external stem colour) were observed during vegetative development.

Statistical analyses

Qualitative collected data were processed using software XLSTAT version 2013.6.04.

They were subjected to the Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) after the descriptive statistics. The MCA is a method used to study the association between two variables. It shows and allows the identifying of factorial axes that reveal the most discriminant variables.

Aggregative Hierarchical Clustering (AHC) allowed the scoring of the classes and indicating of their composition on the basis of the factorial selected axes and dissimilarity level. Class composition was optimized by the analysis of dynamic clusters (k-means).

The matrix of similarity / dissimilarity revealed, within each class, similar accessions (duplicates) suggesting that they had the same scores for all modalities; the euclidean distance calculated within these specimens was zero.

The Chi-2 per box established by the correspondence between the classes and methods of the variables on the basis of a comparison between observed and theoretical numbers (expected)

accessions at the 0.05 level. It allowed the defining of the classes.

For the correspondence between new accessions groups and previous groups living in collection of CNRA, a test of similarity / dissimilarity was done. In this case, the analysis was done with the database of the central individuals of current groups and those central predetermined individuals in previous groups from the collection of CNRA.

RESULTS

Distribution of modalities of the descriptors

Descriptive statistics indicated that each modality was observed among 159 accessions analyzed (Table 2). Modalities such as red or bicolor vein leaf, large mature leaf, lack of flowering, brown epidermis and white pulp were observed over 80% of analyzed accessions. In contrast, less than 10% of individuals had a spreading branching habit, narrow adult leaves, dominant green bicolor petioles, purple apical stem, white epidermis and yellow flesh. The number of accessions to purple apex was approximately equal to that of individuals green apical leaf. The same observation appeared between conical tuberous roots and cylindrical tuberous roots (Table 2).

Description of the most discriminating descriptors and modalities

The Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) brought together the modalities of the variables according to the first six axes namely F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 and F6. These axes represented 51.3% of the total variability (Table 3). Based on the contributions of modalities (Table 4), the six factorial axes were characterized. Thus:

- Axis 1 (F1) explained 11% of the total variability and was defined by the colour of vein and petiole leaves; it contained accessions with green petiole and those with green vein leaves.
- Axis 2 (F2), describing 10% of the variability, was characterized by the colour of vein leaves, the colour of the epidermis and phelloderm tuberous roots. It grouped accessions with dominant red bicolor petiole, those with white epidermis and yellowish phelloderm.
- Axis 3 (F3), expressing 9% of the total variability, was defined by flowering accessions and coloured pulp and mature leaf; it opposed accessions with flower and dark-green mature leaf to yellow pulp.
- Axis 4 (F4), representing 8% of the total variability, was characterized by the colour of the stem and the branching habit at 12 months. It opposed individuals with orange stem to those with erect branching habit.
- Axis 5 (F5), describing 7% of the total variability, was defined by the colour of the apical stem and petioles and shape of mature

leaf. It opposed individuals with purple apical stem and narrow mature leaf to those with dominant green bicolor petiole.

- Axis 6 (F6), representing 6% of the total variability, was characterized by accessions which had white phelloderm by opposing to those with purple apical stem apical.

The Multiple Correspondence Analysis allowed the understanding that 14 modalities out of a total of 35 have better explained the variability within the germplasm.

Classification of accessions

The Aggregative Hierarchical Clustering (AHC) and Analysis of Dynamic Clusters (k-means) carried out on the six factorial axes that defined homogeneous groups of accessions within the cassava collection. A total of 3 classes of accessions were revealed using a level of dissimilarity of 102 (Figure 2). The similarity/dissimilarity matrix allowed specimens to be identified based on all the observed descriptors. According to the test of Chi-2 per box, the variables CLAD, FFAD, FLOR and PORT were independent of classes at the 0.05 level. Each class was characterized by variable categories with frequencies clearly different from other class' frequencies. Each group took the name of the individual who best features (central individual). Thus, the characteristics of the classes thus were defined as follows (Tables 5 and 6):

- Class 1, Sié group, contained 45 accessions. It included all the accessions of germplasm with yellow pulp. It consisted of 91% of accessions yellowish phelloderm, 62% of accessions with white epidermis and 61% of individuals with orange stem.
- Class 2, Bassié djélé4 type, presented the highest number with 87 accessions. All individuals of this class expressed white flesh and red or green-red vein leaves. This type contained 82% of accessions with green-purple apical stem, 72% of accessions with red petioles, 69% of accessions pink phelloderm and 69% of pedunculate accessions and 64% of accessions with green apical leaf.
- Class 3, Djonan djonan group, showed the smallest effective accessions (27). All accessions of this class displayed green apical stem. There were 87% of accessions with green vein leaves and 85% of accessions with green petiole. In this group, 63% of accessions presented dark external stems.

There were duplicates in all classes especially in Class 2 which had the largest number.

Correspondence between new accessions groups and previous groups living collection of CNRA

The test of similarity / dissimilarity (Table 7) showed that 687 of the central individual in Sié class 1 (new collection) was close to the central individual 394 in the Cosca4 (or Agba bana) class 2 (existing collection); Similarly, the 602 from Bassié djélé4 class 2 (new germplasm) was near to 42 of the D14 (or Bonoua rouge) class 6 (existing germplasm). The central individual 605 of Djonan djonan class 3 (new germplasm) was close to 57 of 256 (or TMS30572) class 5 (existing collection).

DISCUSSION

A total of 159 accessions from 26 villages located in three regions of Côte d'Ivoire have been characterized on the basis of qualitative morphological variables. This study highlighted the most discriminating descriptors that have contributed to the formation of the factorial axes. However, all the 35 modalities of 14 variables were observed on individuals. Therefore, morphological variability appeared within the current germplasm. The six first axes represented 51.3% of the total variability and were used for AHC. Indeed, the used variables were also part of the list of morphological selected characters by IITA (Fukuda *et al.*, 2010) for the characterization of cassava. In this study, the frequency of cassava coloured flesh obtained (9%) seems to be small but it was higher than the one obtained by N'Zué (2007) in the collection of CNRA (3%). It was also higher than the maximum 5% obtained in Africa as reported by Nweke *et al.* (1994). According to N'Zué (2007), the scarcity of yellow flesh varieties could be due to the genetic determinism. Regarding this aspect, Iglesias *et al.* (1997) hypothesized the presence of two genes with epistatic effects controlling the tuberous root colour after crossings between white and yellow flesh genotypes. In progeny, the segregation (50 % white, 25 % cream, 25 % yellow) confirmed the hypothesis. Nonetheless, according to the same authors, the same study carried out with parents presenting colour extremes of roots (for example, white and orange) revealed a more complex heredity with more alleles. Furthermore, Ndombo *et al.* (1992) showed that cassava varieties with yellow flesh were rich in provitamin A, calcium and low in hydrocyanic acid.

In addition, duplicates detected in different classes let assume that some accessions are several copies in the collection; that was the case of Koko soclo1, Koko soclo2 and Koko soclo4 from two different villages. This confirms the farmer's nomenclature. Indeed, Elias *et al.* (2001) reported that different cultivars of cassava could present the same name or multiple names could be given to a single cultivar on farm. That could lead to an overestimation or underestimation of the varietal cassava diversity on farm. Therefore, the same duplicates might be a single genotype. Complementary experiments based on enzymatic and molecular characterization could confirm or not this hypothesis.

The studied accessions of current germplasm were clustered into 3 classes at a level of dissimilarity

of 102. In contrary, N'Zué (2007) used the same characters for 340 accessions and has obtained 8 classes at a level of dissimilarity of 5 within the base collection. The difference between the number of classes could be explained by the weak number of accessions used as well as the presence in the germplasm studied of overwhelmingly traditional varieties with little different origins. The basic genebank contained accessions from both traditional and improved varieties from several origins. The relative diversity of the core collection combined with highest number of accessions could explain the greater number of classes.

Establishing the correspondence between current classes and existing clusters, the class 1 (Sié type), class 2 (Bassié djélé4 type) and class 3 (Djonan djonan type) of actual germplasm are respectively close to class 2 (Agba bana type), class 6 (Bonoua rouge type) and class 5 (TMS30572 type) which were classified by N'Zué (2007). Combining the two germplasms, all the 499 accessions might be clustered into eight main groups. Thus, the characteristics of these Groups could be as follows:

- Group 1, 99(41)1 type, including 34 accessions: spread branching habit, orange stem, green-purple apical stem.
- Group 2, Agba bana or Sié type, containing 65 accessions: orange stem, yellowish phelloderm, yellow pulp.
- Group 3, H43 type with 31 accessions: yellowish stem, purple apical stem, predominantly cylindrical tuberous roots.
- Group 4, TMS30001 type, including 35 accessions: yellowish stem, white epidermis, white phelloderm.
- Group 5, TMS30572 or Djonan djonan type, including 86 accessions: green petiole, green vein leaf, dark external stem.
- Group 6, Bassié djélé4 or Bonoua rouge type, presenting the highest number with 153 accessions: light green leaf, red or green-red vein leaves, red petiole, green apical leaf, green-purple apical stem, pedunculate, pink phelloderm. According to Ivorian farmers and households, varieties with pink phelloderm, mostly in this Group, are multi purposes (foutou, attiéké, dough-like toh or placali, gari, flour, starch, etc.). This justified their conservative selection on farm.
- Group 7, CB2 type with 52 accessions: narrow leaf, purple apical leaf, yellow phelloderm.
- Group 8, Gbéritingué type including 43 accessions: erect branching habit, predominantly red bi-coloured petiole, predominantly conical tuberous roots, white phelloderm.

CONCLUSION

A total of 159 accessions of cassava from the Centre-west, South-west and West of Côte d'Ivoire have been characterized by morphological traits. The study highlighted the variability within the germplasm collected. The 159 accessions of the 3 regions were clustered into three classes instead of eight classes. It revealed that the germplasm collected contained 143 morphotypes and 16 duplicates. The three classes obtained in the study were similar to three out of eight classes from the base collection.

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Table 1: Codes and scale scores of qualitative descriptors of cassava (N'Zué, 2007)

Type of descriptors	Descriptors observed	Code	Modalities	score
Leaf and stem descriptors (observations at 5 months)	Apical leaf colour	CAPE	purple green	1 2
	Vein leaf colour	CNFE	green other (red, green-red)	1 2
	Petiole colour	CPET	red green bi-colour (red>green) bi-colour (red<green)	1 2 3 4
	Mature leaf colour	CLAD	dark green light green	1 2
	Shape of mature leaf (lobes)	FFAD	narrow large	1 2
	Apical stem colour	CJTA	purple green green-purple	1 2 3
	Tuberous roots descriptors (observations at harvesting (12 months))	Peduncle	LPED	sessile, short pedunculate
Shape of tuberous roots		FRTU	conical dominant cylindrical dominant	1 2
Epidermis colour of tuberous roots		CEPI	brown white	1 2
Phelloderm colour		CPHE	pink white yellowish	1 2 3
Pulp colour		CCHA	white yellow	1 2
Other descriptors	Flowering	FLOR	presence absence	1 2
	Branching habit at 12 months	PORT	spread semi-spread erect	1 2 3
	External stem colour at 12 months	CTIG	dark grey orange yellowish	1 2 3 4

Table 2: Relative frequencies of different modalities estimated from 14 qualitative descriptors observed on 159 cassava accessions

Descriptors observed	code		Relative frequencies (%)
Apical leaf colour	CAPE	purple	44
		green	56
Vein leaf colour	CNFE	green	19
		other (red, green-red)	81
Petiole colour	CPET	red	69
		green	17
		red>green	12
		red<green	2
Mature leaf colour	CLAD	dark-green	42
		light green	58
Apical stem colour	CJTA	purple or red	8
		green	61
		green-red or green-purple	31
Shape of mature leaf	FFAD	narrow (L/l) \geq 6)	4
		large (L/l) \leq 6)	96
Flowering until harvest	FLOR	presence	20
		absence	80
Branching habit at 12 months	PORT	spreading	8
		semi-spreading	60
		erect	32
External stem colour at 12 month	CTIG	dark	36
		grey	40
		orange	11
		yellowish	13
Peduncle	LPED	sessile, short	46
		pedunculate (>10 cm)	54
Shape of tuberous roots	FRTU	conical dominant	37
		cylindrical dominant	63
Epidermis colour of tuberous roots	CEPI	brown	92
		white	8
Phelloderm colour	CPHE	pink	57
		white	22
		yellowish	21
Pulp (or flesh) colour	CCHA	white	91
		yellow	9

Table 3: Eigen values of factorial axes

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	
Eigen values	0.165	0.143	0.137	0.126	0.106	0.093	0.076	0.075	0.068	0.066	
Inertie (%)	10.981	9.531	9.157	8.405	7.088	6.186	5.082	4.988	4.510	4.394	
Cumulative %	10.981	20.511	29.669	38.073	45.162	51.348	56.430	61.418	65.928	70.322	
	F11	F12	F13	F14	F15	F16	F17	F18	F19	F20	F21
Eigen values	0.063	0.062	0.053	0.050	0.047	0.042	0.035	0.031	0.027	0.022	0.013
Inertie (%)	4.221	4.113	3.524	3.350	3.107	2.802	2.366	2.091	1.800	1.441	0.862
Cumulative %	74.544	78.657	82.181	85.530	88.637	91.440	93.806	95.897	97.697	99.138	100.000

Table 4: Contributions of variables and their modalities to the formation of the factorial axes

Factorial axis	Variable	Contribution of variables (%)	Modality	Contribution of modalities (%)
F1	CNFE	26.6	CNFE-1	21.6
	CPET	29	CPET-2	21.5
F2	CPET	14.7	CPET-3	8
	CEPI	12	CEPI-2	11
	CPHE	16.2	CPHE-3	10.7
F3	CLAD	19	CLAD-1	11
	FLOR	20	FLOR-1	16
	CCHA	15.7	CCHA-2	14.2
F4	PORT	15.1	PORT-3	8.4
	CTIG	16.1	CTIG-3	10.1
F5	CPET	10.8	CPET-4	8.2
	CJTA	11.8	CJTA-1	10.4
	FFAD	16.7	FFAD-1	16.1
F6	CPHE	36.4	CPHE-2	28.3

Legend: Codes of variables and modalities are summarized in table 2

Table 5: Characteristics of classes according to the Khi-2 test per box

Class	CAPE		CNFE		CPET			
	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	4
C1	3.968	-3.968	-2.021	2.021	-0.322	-2.645	3.594	-0.148
C2	-2.664	2.664	-6.684	6.684	6.643	-5.420	-2.650	-1.209
C3	-1.228	1.228	11.286	-11.286	-8.420	10.359	-0.799	1.781

Class	CJTA			CTIG				LPED	
	1	2	3	1	2	3	4	1	2
C1	1.735	0.919	-1.953	-4.821	1.395	3.281	1.773	2.946	-2.946
C2	-0.341	-4.271	4.681	1.931	0.319	-1.433	-1.895	-3.818	3.818
C3	-1.629	4.559	-3.862	3.224	-2.097	-2.038	0.385	1.527	-1.527

Class	FRTU		CEPI		CPHE			FFAD	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	1	2
C1	3.390	-3.390	-2.776	2.776	-5.851	-2.084	9.179	-0.645	0.645
C2	-2.402	2.402	2.392	-2.392	4.100	1.480	-6.452	1.436	-1.436
C3	-0.883	0.883	0.160	-0.160	1.584	0.539	-2.459	-1.129	1.129

Class	FLOR		PORT			CCHA		CLAD	
	1	2	1	2	3	1	2	1	2
C1	-1.342	1.342	1.735	-0.781	-0.164	-6.478	6.478	0.370	-0.370
C2	0.990	-0.990	-0.341	-0.172	0.374	4.474	-4.474	-1.181	1.181
C3	0.298	-0.298	-1.629	1.165	-0.299	1.841	-1.841	1.122	-1.122

Adjusted residuals (Pearson) (class / variable): Values in bold are significant at alpha = 0.05. The modalities that have adjusted residuals in bold characterize classes. More the residual value is positively high, the better the class which is characterized by this modality. More values are negative, the higher the class contains less accession with this modality. Other modalities are independent of classes and they have not characterized.

Table 6: Characteristics of classes obtained after optimization by partitional clustering and Chi-2 per box

Class	Central individual (name)	Total number	Duplicated accessions by class	Dominant morphological characteristics
C1	687 (Sié)	45	613 ¹ , 640 ¹ , 703 ² , 705 ²	yellow pulp, white epidermis, yellowish phelloderm, orange stem
C2	602 (Bassié djélé 4)	87	600 ¹ , 602 ² , 607 ³ , 619 ³ , 620 ² , 633 ⁴ , 638 ⁴ , 644 ⁵ , 645 ³ , 655 ² , 665 ¹ , 667 ⁵ , 672 ⁶ , 673 ⁶ , 681 ⁷ , 688 ⁶ , 693 ⁷ , 695 ⁸ , 696 ⁹ , 699 ⁹ , 715 ⁸	white pulp, green apical leaf, red petiole, red-green or purple-green apical stem, red or green-red vein leaf
C3	605 (Djonan djonan)	27	643 ¹ , 656 ¹ , 661 ¹	green petiole, green vein leaf, green apical stem, dark external stem

In each line, accessions with same superscript number are specimens.

Table 7: Proximity matrix of central individuals from three current classes and from height existing classes in bold (general dissimilarity at 0.95 level)

	212	394	64	258	57	42	46	399	687	602	605
212	0										
394	0.500	0									
64	0.357	0.500	0								
258	0.357	0.500	0.571	0							
57	0.357	0.571	0.357	0.214	0						
42	0.286	0.286	0.357	0.286	0.357	0					
46	0.357	0.571	0.357	0.500	0.429	0.357	0				
399	0.286	0.429	0.357	0.429	0.214	0.357	0.429	0			
687	0.429	0.214	0.429	0.571	0.643	0.357	0.500	0.500	0		
602	0.429	0.286	0.357	0.429	0.500	0.143	0.500	0.357	0.357	0	
605	0.500	0.500	0.429	0.357	0.143	0.357	0.571	0.214	0.571	0.357	0

Highlighted values in yellow colour showed the relative proximity of a central individual belonging to current class and the second belonging to the existing class.

Figure 1 : Collect and trial sites in Côte d'Ivoire

Legend

Figure 2: Dendrogramme revealing 3 classes at a dissimilarity level of 102

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